

1 **Production of amphidinols and other bioproducts of interest by the marine**
2 **microalga *Amphidinium carterae* unraveled by NMR metabolomics approach**
3 **coupled to multivariate data analysis**

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26 **ABSTRACT**

27 This study assessed the feasibility of an NMR metabolomics approach coupled to
28 multivariate data analysis to monitor the naturally present or stresses-elicited metabolites,
29 from a long-term (>170 days) culture of the dinoflagellate marine microalgae
30 *Amphidinium carterae* grown in a fiberglass paddlewheel-driven raceway
31 photobioreactor (PBR). Metabolic contents particularly on two members of the
32 amphidinol family, amphidinol A and its 7-sulfate derivative amphidinol B, (referred as
33 APDs) and other compounds of interest (fatty acids, carotenoids, oxylipins, etc.) were
34 evaluated by altering concentration levels of the f/2 medium nutrients and daily mean
35 irradiance. Operating with a 24 h sinusoidal light cycle allowed a 3-fold increase on APDs
36 production, which was also detected by an increase on hemolytic activity of methanolic
37 extract of *A. carterae* biomass. The presence of APDs was consistent with the antitumoral
38 activity measured in the methanolic extracts of biomass. Increased daily irradiance was
39 accompanied by a general decrease on pigments and an increase on SFAs, MUFAs and
40 DHA, while increased nutrient availability lead to an increase of sugars, amino acids,
41 PUFA ω -3 contents and of pigments and a decrease on SFAs and MUFAs. NMR-based
42 metabolomics showed to be a fast and suitable method to accompany the production of
43 APDs and bioactive compounds without the need of tedious isolation methods and
44 bioassays. The two APDs compounds were chemically identified by spectroscopic NMR
45 and spectrometric ESI-IT MS and ESI-TOF-MS methods.

46

47 **Keywords**

48 NMR; Metabolomics; Multivariate Data Analysis; Amphidinols; Microalgae;
49 Dinoflagellates; Photobioreactor; *Amphidinium carterae*; Carotenoids; Fatty acids,
50 Oxylipins

51 INTRODUCTION

52 Marine dinoflagellate microalgae are a source of impressive and fascinating bioactive
53 compounds.¹⁻² The production of compounds differs according to the microalgae used.³
54 In particular, *Amphidinium carterae* produces an interesting group of polyketide
55 metabolites, namely amphidinolides and amphidinols (henceforth referred to as APDs
56 indistinctly). APDs elicit potent anticancer, antifungal and hemolytic activities, thus are
57 potentially useful in studies of rational drug design.⁴ Nuzzo, *et al.*⁵ have described the
58 presence of two new polyketides of the amphidinol family, amphidinol 18 (AM18) and
59 its corresponding 7-sulfate derivative (AM19), in the MeOH extract of the dinoflagellate
60 *A. carterae*. Three years later, Cutignano, *et al.*⁶ found amphidinol A and its 7-sulfate
61 derivative (amphidinol B), from a dinoflagellate strain of *A. carterae* isolated from Fusaro
62 Lake, a brackish lagoon near Naples (Italy).

63 Carotenoids from marine dinoflagellate microalgae are also manifold. *A. carterae* has
64 been reported to produce significant amounts of peridinin, which is a unique marker
65 pigment in most dinoflagellates with interesting technological applications, derived from
66 their unique photophysical properties, and with potential use in medicine as therapeutic
67 agent against different diseases.⁷⁻¹⁰ Besides, most microalgae represent a viable
68 alternative source for a great variety of lipids. From a nutritional point of view, essential
69 fatty acids (FA) including unsaturated FAs (UFAs), are vital for the proper functioning
70 of the human body, have protective effects against atherosclerotic heart disease, and in
71 prevention of chronic diseases.¹¹ *A. carterae* is a producer of the omega-3 polyunsaturated
72 fatty acids (PUFAs) eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA),¹²
73 which hold enormous nutraceutical and pharmaceutical applications.¹³

74 Until recently, the lack of custom-made methods for successfully culturing
75 dinoflagellates in industrial-scale photobioreactors (PBRs) represented a hurdle to the

76 production of large amounts of bioactive compounds because of their high sensitivity to
77 damage by hydrodynamics stresses.¹⁴ Recent studies have demonstrated that this shear-
78 sensitive marine dinoflagellate microalgae, including *A. carterae*, can be successfully
79 cultured in pilot-scale bubble column and raceway PBRs illuminated with multi-color
80 LEDs in the modes batch, fed-batch and semicontinuous.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ So far, the valorization of
81 the harvested microalgae biomass has been mostly performed on the basis of
82 quantification of specific metabolites commonly by targeted approaches using LC-MS
83 and GC-MS. Concerning the APDs, its content on microalgae biomass has been indirectly
84 measured by hemolytic and antiproliferative assays, which are time-consuming and
85 tedious techniques.

86 In this study, we aim to develop a simple, untargeted and fast method able to
87 characterize at once the metabolic profile of the marine dinoflagellate *A. carterae*,
88 especially on its APDs content. For this, we have applied a metabolomic approach based
89 on the use of NMR spectroscopy coupled to several multivariate data analysis techniques.
90 For the structural elucidation of the proposed APDs structures, high resolution mass
91 spectrometry (HR-MS) and tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) were also applied. The
92 biomass used in this study was obtained from a long-term (>170 days) culture developed
93 in a LED-based raceway photobioreactor as recently reported.¹⁷

94 In the chemical ecology of marine algae, comparative metabolomics has recently
95 gained importance since it helps to overcome limitations of traditional bioassay-guided
96 structure elucidation approaches, which involve multiple rounds of separation of the
97 crude extract and testing until the identification of the target molecule is achieved.¹⁸
98 Broader use of metabolomics can thus provide in-depth knowledge on *A. carterae*
99 biomass composition and its nutritional value and generate comprehensive data on its
100 metabolic networks. It offers a unique opportunity to explore in an untargeted way the

101 final products of cellular metabolism and, therefore, to reveal the metabolic transition
102 before and after exposure response to a variety of environmental conditions and stresses.
103 Such information is helpful in setting the appropriate culture conditions to enrich and
104 preserve the biomass with certain desired metabolites, by diverting the metabolism
105 towards the desired pathways or slowing down the undesired pathways. For example, the
106 biosynthesis of lipids, pigments and polyketide metabolites (e.g. biotoxins) in microalgae
107 may be tuned by using operational and abiotic stress factors.¹⁹⁻²⁰ We have recently shown
108 the capacity of ¹H NMR metabolomics to successfully monitor metabolic shifts of
109 *Isochrysis galbana* when varying culture conditions such as temperature and light
110 irradiance.²¹ To the best of our knowledge, we report herein the first application of an
111 NMR-based metabolomic approach to describe both polar and non-polar metabolic
112 profile of *A. carterae* especially on APDs molecules and how it can be affected overtime
113 by environmental changes and cultivation conditions (increased daily irradiance and
114 nutrient availability).

115

116 MATERIALS AND METHODS

117 **The microalga.** *Amphidinium carterae* Dn241EHU was the marine microalgae used
118 in this study. It is deposited in the microalgae culture collection of the plant biology and
119 ecology department of the university of the Basque country. The morphological
120 characteristics and genetic identification of this strain have been previously reported.²²
121 Inoculum were grown in f/2 medium as described elsewhere.¹⁷

122 **Production of microalgal biomass.** The biomass used in the work presented herein
123 was produced in a LED-based raceway photobioreactor. The PBR configuration,
124 dimensions, details about the culture system and experimental strategy were previously
125 reported.¹⁷ Briefly, the culture surface was illuminated using multicolor LED strips (red,

126 green, blue and warm white, collectively referred to as RGBW; Edison Opto Co., Taiwan).
127 Water losses due to evaporation were automatically compensated by adding sterile
128 distilled water. The pH and temperature were maintained at 8.5 and 21 ± 1 °C respectively.
129 The biomass was obtained from 5 experimental sets carried out in semicontinuous mode
130 operation, which consisted in removing a culture volume and replenishing with an equal
131 volume of fresh medium once the culture entered a stationary phase caused by depleting
132 nitrate-N or phosphate-P in supernatants.¹⁷ The f/2 medium was used as a basis for
133 assaying different nutrient concentrations. The composition of the f/2 medium
134 composition was as follows: NaNO_3 , 882 μM ; $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 36.2 μM ; $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$,
135 106 μM ; $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 11.7 μM ; $\text{Na}_2\text{EDTA} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 11.7 μM ; $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.04 μM ;
136 $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.03 μM ; $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.08 μM ; $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.04 μM ; $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$,
137 0.9 μM ; Thiamine, 0.3 μM ; Biotin, 2.1 nM; B12, 0.37 nM.²³ The fresh medium was
138 supplemented with nutrients as extensively detailed elsewhere.¹⁷ Different initial
139 concentration levels of the f/2 medium nutrients (i.e. f/2 \times 1 to 3) were assayed. A
140 sinusoidal diel variation pattern of irradiance was imposed, with a maximum irradiance
141 occurring at midday (I_{omax}) of 900 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. Three diel variation patterns of irradiance
142 (light/dark cycles: 12:12, 18:6 and 24:0 hours) that supplied different daily mean
143 irradiance (Y_0) were evaluated. The complete operational strategy is summarized in detail
144 in Table 1. The biomass used in this work was prepared as previously reported.¹⁵ In short,
145 suspensions of *A. carterae* (volumes of ca. 250 mL) were gently centrifuged (700g, 8
146 min) in sterile 250 mL Falcon tubes. The pellets were gently washed with 40 mL of
147 distilled water. Cells were again pelleted, the supernatants carefully removed, and the
148 tubes were dried in a vacuum freeze-dryer (Cryodos 50, Telstar) for 48 h. Lyophilized
149 algal powders were stored in a desiccator until use. For comparison purposes, the
150 following combinations of sets were selected on the basis of the effect of the factors

151 explored with them (Table 1): (i) sets 1 and 2 were used to compare the effect of Y_o
152 corresponding to the irradiance diel variation patterns of 12:12 and 18:6, respectively,
153 using $f/2 \times 1$ (N:P=5) as culture medium; (ii) sets 4 and 5 were used to compare the effect
154 of Y_o corresponding to the irradiance diel variation patterns of 18:6 and 24:0, respectively,
155 using $f/2 \times 3$ (N:P=5) as culture medium; (iii) sets 2, 3 and 4 were used to evaluate the
156 effect of the proportion of $f/2$ nutrients added (i.e. $f/2 \times 1$, $\times 2$ and $\times 3$) at a fixed value of
157 Y_o .

158 **Hemolytic activity assay.** APDs are contained in the cells and a part of them is
159 released to the supernatants. Since these compounds show varied levels of hemolytic
160 activity, titers of them were expressed in terms of hemolytic activity of cell extracts on
161 erythrocytes from defibrinated sheep blood as described elsewhere.^{15, 24} In short, from
162 dose-response Hill curves, values of EC50 for *A. carterae* (i.e. number of cells per well
163 giving 50% hemolysis) and saponin control were calculated. Saponin was supplied by
164 Sigma Aldrich (47036, CAS n° 8047-15-2, Saint Louis, MO, USA) and the corresponding
165 EC50 was of $8.5 \times 10^6 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$ pg per well. An equivalent saponin potency (ESP)
166 expressed in terms pg saponin per *A. carterae* cell was calculated by dividing the EC50
167 for saponin by the EC50 for *A. carterae*.

168 ***In vitro* anticancer activity assay.** Antiproliferative assays for crude methanolic
169 extracts obtained from *A. carterae* biomass were performed as described elsewhere.²⁵⁻²⁶
170 Four human tumor cell lines obtained from the American Type Culture Collection
171 (ATCC), namely A549 (ATCC CCL-185) (lung carcinoma, NSCLC), HT-29 (ATCC
172 HTB-38) (colon adenocarcinoma), MDA-MB-231 (ATCC HTB-26) (breast
173 adenocarcinoma) and PSN-1 (ATCC CRL-3211) (pancreas adenocarcinoma), were used.
174 Cells were maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented
175 with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), 2mM L-glutamine, 100 U/mL penicillin and 100

176 U/mL streptomycin at 37 °C, 5% CO₂ and 98% humidity. For the experiments, cells were
177 harvested from subconfluent cultures by trypsinization and resuspended in fresh medium
178 before counting and plating. Human tumor cells were seeded in 96-well microtiter plates,
179 at 5000 cells per well in aliquots of 150 μL and allowed to attach to the plate surface for
180 18 h (overnight) in drug-free medium. One control (untreated) plate for each cell line was
181 then fixed and used for the time zero reference value. Cells on plates were then exposed
182 to different methanolic extract concentrations in DMSO/DMEM (10, 30 and 100 μg mL⁻¹).
183 Cell survival was measured after treatment for 72 h. Results are provided as survival
184 percentages: 100% means there are as many cells as the control (extracts does not inhibit
185 growth); 0% means that there is the same number of cells as those at the start of the trial
186 (no growth, extracts inhibit mitosis); -50% means a reduction in the number of cells of
187 50% compared to the start of the trial (moderate cytotoxic effect); -100% means that the
188 all cells were lysed (strong cytotoxic effect). Measurements were performed for duplicate
189 samples. The standard deviations were in most cases less than 10%.

190 **Sample preparation for NMR.** Eight biological replicates were prepared for *A.*
191 *carterae* freeze-dried biomass samples collected from 5 different experimental sets. Two
192 solvent systems were chosen to stretch as much as possible the number of identified
193 metabolites and optimize the extraction of the APDs: (1) a mixture of CH₃OH-*d*₄ and
194 phosphate D₂O buffer solution at pH 6 (80:20, v/v), containing the sodium salt of 3-
195 (trimethylsilyl)propionic-2,2,3,3-*d*₄ acid (TSP, 0.01%_{w/w}) and sodium azide (NaN₃, 90
196 μM) as an enzyme inhibitor; (2) a mixture of CDCl₃ containing the
197 tetrakis(trimethylsilyl)silane (TTMS, 1.2 mM) and CH₃OH-*d*₄ in 80:20 (v/v) ratio. Thirty
198 milligrams of microalgal biomass samples were extracted using 0.8 mL of each solvent
199 by sonicating the mixtures in an ultrasound bath (20 min, 25 °C), followed by vortexing
200 (600 rpm, 10 min), and centrifugation (13,500 rpm, 5 min). Eight biological replicates of

201 biomass from each set (in a total of 40 samples) were extracted with each solvent system.
202 Five hundred microliters of the supernatants were transferred in oven-dried 5 mm NMR
203 tubes for spectral analysis.

204 **NMR spectra.** Biomass extracts were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 600
205 spectrometer operating at a proton frequency of 600 MHz and using a 5 mm QCI
206 quadruple resonance pulse field gradient cryoprobe. All spectra were acquired without
207 rotation at 293 ± 0.1 K and using a NOESY presaturation pulse sequence (Bruker 1D
208 noesygppr1d) with water suppression via irradiation of the water frequency during the
209 recycle and mixing time delays. The pulse conditions for both methanol:water (80:20 v/v)
210 and chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extracts were as follows: number of scans = 32, size
211 of fid = 64K, spectral width = 20.0 ppm, acquisition time = 2.73 s, relaxation delay = 5 s,
212 FID resolution = 0.37 Hz, mixing time = 10 ms and receiver gain = 57. The spectra were
213 automatically phased, baseline-corrected, and calibrated to the TSP and TTMS signals
214 both located at 0.0 ppm for methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and chloroform:methanol (80:20
215 v/v) extracts, respectively. Acquisition and processing of NMR spectra were carried out
216 using TOPSPIN software (version 3.1). The spectra were shimmed through topshim and
217 acquired using an NMR samplecase that allowed the automatic analysis of 24 samples in
218 a row.

219 Additionally, ^1H - ^1H correlation spectroscopy (COSY), ^1H - ^1H total correlation
220 spectroscopy (TOCSY), ^1H - ^{13}C heteronuclear single quantum coherence (HSQC) and ^1H -
221 ^{13}C heteronuclear multiple bonds coherence (HMBC) spectra were recorded using
222 standard Bruker sequences. COSY spectrum was obtained with a D1 of 1 s, SW in both
223 dimensions of 9,014.40 Hz, a receiver gain (RG) of 203 and it was processed using sine
224 window function (SSB = 0.0). TOCSY spectrum was obtained with D1 of 1.5 s, SW of
225 9,009.01 Hz in both dimensions, RG of 64 and processed using quadratic sine window

226 function (SSB = 2.0). The HSQC spectrum was acquired using a D1 of 1.0 s, SW of
227 7,211.54 Hz in F2 and 34,710.77 Hz in F1 and processed using a quadratic sine window
228 function (SSB = 2.0). The HMBC spectrum was recorded with the same parameters used
229 in the HSQC spectra except for 36,219.57 Hz of spectral width in F1. The delays of
230 coupling evolution were optimized for $^1J_{\text{CH}} = 145$ Hz and $^nJ_{\text{CH}} = 8$ Hz.

231 **Data analysis and statistics.** To prepare NMR data for multivariate modeling, the
232 collected spectra were aligned and reduced into spectral bins of 0.04 ppm widths by using
233 AMIX 3.9.12 (Bruker BioSpin GmbH, Rheinstetten, Germany). The area under each bin
234 was integrated. The intensity of individual peaks was scaled to the total intensity recorded
235 in the region from δ_{H} 0.2 to 10.0 ppm. The regions of δ_{H} 5.08–4.60, 3.36–3.28 and 7.32–
236 7.24 ppm were excluded from the analysis because of the suppression signal of water and
237 the residual signals of methanol and chloroform, respectively. The resulting data matrices
238 consisted of rows representing observations/samples and columns representing spectral
239 regions. Both data matrices obtained for methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and
240 chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extracts were combined and analyzed together by
241 multivariate data analysis methods with SIMCA-P software (v. 14.0, Umetrics, Sweden).
242 NMR data were analyzed by means of the unsupervised technique Principal Component
243 Analysis (PCA) and the supervised technique Partial Least Squares (PLS). PCA model
244 was scaled by Pareto whereas PLS by Unit Variance (UV). PLS models were validated
245 by the permutation test with a permutation number of 100. The models shown in Figures
246 8 and 9 were validated using permutation test with 100 permutations and validated when
247 R2-intercept does not exceed 0.4-0.5 and Q2-intercept does not exceed 0.05.²⁷ The
248 intercepts of R2 and Q2 generated for each extract were 0.322 and -0.331 and 0.404 and
249 -0.259 for both models, respectively, further proving their robustness. To visualize the
250 relationship among samples, hierarchical clustering was performed, and heat maps were

251 created using the Statistical analysis tool in MetaboAnalyst 4.0 software,²⁸⁻²⁹ which were
252 based on the Euclidean distance measure and the Ward clustering algorithm. The
253 displayed metabolites were selected by analysis of variance (ANOVA) using a
254 significance level of $P < 0.05$, and post-hoc analysis based on Fisher’s Least Significant
255 Difference (LSD).

256 **ESI-IT MS and ESI-TOF MS experiments.** To identify the APDs, infusion MS
257 experiments were carried out by using low- and high-resolution MS. MS analysis was
258 performed to biomass $\text{CH}_3\text{OH-d}_4$ and phosphate D_2O buffer (80:20, v/v) extracts (as
259 previously explained) diluted by 1:10. A Bruker Daltonics Esquire 2000™ Ion Trap MS
260 (Bruker Daltonik, Bremen, Germany) with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source was
261 used for evaluation of APDs fragmentation patterns, whereas a QTOF SYNAPT G2 MS
262 (Waters) equipped with an ESI interface made possible obtaining the accurate m/z signals
263 of the compounds under study. Bruker MS was controlled using the software Esquire
264 Control and the resulting files were treated with Data Analysis 4.0 (Bruker). Data
265 processing of the Waters spectrometer was conducted with the software MassLynx 4.1
266 (Waters).

267 MS conditions were optimized by continuous infusion (at a flow rate of 120 $\mu\text{L/h}$) of
268 1:10 diluted extracts of biomass samples containing APDs. In ESI-IT MS, analyses were
269 made both in negative and positive polarity with a scan range from 50 to 2000 m/z . The
270 end plate offset voltage was set at -500 V and the capillary voltage at +3500 V in negative
271 polarity, and -3500 V in positive polarity, respectively. Optimum values for the ESI
272 source parameters were: 250°C of drying gas temperature, 5 L/min of drying gas flow and
273 5 psi of nebulizer pressure. Oct RF was set at 300 Vpp and Target mass was fixed at 1500
274 m/z . To perform MS/MS analysis, the cut off energy and the amplitude value of the IT

275 were set between 206 and 398 and between 0.45 and 1.25 V, respectively, for achieving
276 clear fragmentation patterns depending on the selected precursor ions.

277 The ionization parameters were then transferred to the ESI-QTOF spectrometer, which
278 operated in negative and positive polarity too. Source and desolvation temperatures were
279 set at 100 and 500 °C, respectively, and 100 L h⁻¹ of cone gas flow and 1000 L h⁻¹ of
280 desolvation gas flow were used.

281 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

282 **Hemolytic activity of *A. carterae* biomass.** Although several polyketide metabolites
283 compounds isolated from different *Amphidinium* strains have been reported in literature,
284 not all clones produce the same compounds, are cytotoxic and/or show the same
285 bioactivities.³⁰⁻³¹ To investigate the presence of APDs on microalgal biomass, hemolytic
286 activity of cell extracts has been used as a proxy of the levels of APDs in cells.³² Samples
287 of *A. carterae* biomass were collected during its cultivation on a LED-based race-way
288 PBR varying daily irradiance and nutrient availability conditions in a total of five
289 experimental sets (described in Table 1). Figure 1 shows the cell EC50 and average
290 equivalent saponin potency (ESP) throughout the whole culture of *A. carterae* during the
291 5 experimental sets. It is notorious the increase on hemolytic activity of *A. carterae*
292 biomass along cultivation time, especially from set 4 to set 5 (nearly 3-fold), marked by
293 the increase on the irradiance diel variation patterns from 18:6 to 24:0 (light/dark cycles),
294 respectively, and using f/2 × 3 (N:P=5) as culture medium. At set 5, hemolytic activity
295 reached its maximum with a value of 2103 ± 440 pg cell⁻¹, close to 5-fold greater compared
296 to that reported by Molina-Miras, *et al.*¹⁵ for other strain of *A. carterae*. So it seems that
297 this methodology favored the APDs biosynthesis, without the need to establish a long
298 steady-state phase, as was previously demonstrated for *A. carterae* cultured in fed-batch
299 mode with pulse feeding strategy.¹⁵

300 **Antiproliferative activity of *A. carterae* biomass.** The biomass harvested from all
301 sets also presented strong antiproliferative activity (<-80%) against to the four tumor cell
302 lines used and the three methanolic extract concentrations selected (10, 30 and 100 μg
303 mL^{-1}). This is consistent with the hemolytic activity observed by the presence of APDs.
304 Virtually no cell antiproliferative selectivity was obtained. Although several polyketide
305 metabolites isolated from different *Amphidinium* strains have been reported in the
306 literature, not all clones produce the same compounds, are cytotoxic and/or show the same
307 bioactivities.³⁰ These results confirm the potential use of the polyketide metabolites
308 generated by *Amphidinium* in the biomedical industry. Moreover, the successful culture
309 in a conventional photobioreactor may represent a basis for the medium-large scale
310 supply of these compounds.

311 **Metabolic profile of chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) *A. carterae* biomass**
312 **extracts.** Generally, the rather complex matrix of the seawater-based cultivation broth of
313 marine microalgae represents a certain challenge for identification, ranging from highly
314 polar zwitterionic metabolites to entirely hydrophobic hydrocarbons, or from small
315 molecules to higher molecular weight compounds such as lipids. Extraction techniques
316 have thus to cover a broad spectrum of metabolites so those relevant to our study shall be
317 universally covered. To recover non-polar metabolites, samples were extracted using
318 $\text{CDCl}_3:\text{CD}_3\text{OD}$ (80:20, v/v) solvent system. The assignments made on this
319 chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extract of *A. carterae* are represented in Figure 2 and
320 include mostly fatty acids and pigments.

321 With the help of TOCSY (example in Figure S1) and HSQC (example in Figure S2)
322 correlations, most of the fatty acids (FAs) content could be unravel (Table 2). According
323 to Molina-Miras, *et al.*¹⁷, FAs present in the biomass of *A. carterae* cultured in
324 semicontinuous mode comprised several saturated fatty acids (SFAs), mainly

325 hexadecenoic acid (16:0), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs), such as oleic acid
326 (18:1*n*9), and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), mostly DHA (22:6*n*3) and EPA
327 (20:5*n*3), but also stearidonic acid (SDA; 18:4*n*3). Some of these fatty acids are common
328 among several microalgae strains. For instance, EPA and DHA were detected in many of
329 microalgae strains,³³⁻³⁴ such as *I. galbana* ethanolic and methanolic extracts.³⁵⁻³⁶ The
330 amount and types of PUFAs depends on the culture conditions. In the present study, EPA
331 was present at lower concentration than DHA. The level of EPA depends on the
332 elongation of EPA into DPA before subsequent desaturation into DHA by $\Delta 6$ desaturase
333 in the pathway for the biosynthesis of omega-3 long chain-PUFA.³⁷ Similarly, the amount
334 of EPA in Tahitian strain of *I. galbana* (clone T-iso) was also detected at very low level
335 than DHA.³⁸ On the contrary, in another study, the same strain was reported with higher
336 EPA content than DHA.³⁹

337 The $-\text{CH}_3$ terminal group resonance of all fatty acids (mostly MUFAs and SFAs) for
338 *A. carterae*, appeared at δ_{H} 0.87 ppm (triplet, $J = 7.6$ Hz), except for $-\text{CH}_3$ group of the
339 ω -3 fatty acids (EPA, DHA and SDA) that shows up at δ_{H} 0.96 ppm (triplet, $J = 7.0$ Hz).
340 These types of ω -3 fatty acids contain a double bond close to the terminal $-\text{CH}_3$ group
341 that causes that shifts to higher frequencies in the spectrum. In particular, the signal at δ_{H}
342 0.87 ppm has in the TOCSY spectrum several cross peaks with protons located at δ_{H} 1.29,
343 1.60, and 2.28 ppm (Figure S2), which correspond to the saturated chain spin system of
344 FAs. The observed cross peaks between the signal at δ_{H} 0.96 ppm and resonances located
345 at δ_{H} 2.07, 2.78 and 5.35 ppm are indicative of the presence of polyunsaturated lipid
346 chains, such as DHA and EPA (Figure S2). The $-\text{CH}_2-\text{COOR}$ protons of all FAs result
347 in a composite signal at δ_{H} 2.28 ppm while for DHA this signal appears at δ_{H} 2.36 ppm
348 (and at δ_{C} 33.8 ppm in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum) due to the combined deshielding effect of
349 the COOH group and the double bond in γ position respect to COOH group. This

350 chemical shift is highly diagnostic for the presence of DHA in complex mixture analysis.
351 The same occurs with the $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{COOR}$ protons of EPA (triplet at δ_{H} 1.68 ppm)
352 which is well separated from the triplet at δ_{H} 1.60 ppm originated by other fatty acids.
353 Methylene and methine protons of glycerol backbone from triacylglycerides (TAGs) and
354 diacylglycerols (DGs) give rise to two doublets of doublets at δ_{H} 4.30 and 4.16 ppm, and
355 at δ_{H} 4.31 and 4.21 ppm, respectively, while the methine protons appear at δ_{H} 5.26 ppm
356 and 5.08 ppm, respectively.

357 The sterolic composition of *A. carterae* biomass could be determined by observing
358 singlets in the δ_{H} 0.6–0.75 ppm spectral region which belong to CH_3 -18. In fact, the ^1H
359 NMR spectrum shows a characteristic high-intensity resonance at δ_{H} 0.73 ppm, due to the
360 CH_3 -18 of cholesterol. All the given assignments were verified further by 2D
361 experiments.

362 The downfield region starting from 5.5 ppm of the ^1H NMR spectra of the
363 chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extracts of *A. carterae* biomass spectra indicated the
364 signals for carotenoids and chlorophylls constituents that were mainly ascribed to
365 chlorophyll a and peridinin (Figure 2), which was reported as the major pigments
366 identified in *A. carterae* biomass.¹⁷ These photosynthetic pigments are valuable bioactive
367 compounds and are abundant in microalgae.⁴⁰⁻⁴¹ Singlets at δ_{H} 9.35 (δ_{C} 97.0 ppm), 9.49
368 (δ_{C} 104.2 ppm), and 8.54 ppm (δ_{C} 93.5 ppm) shown in Figure 2 were assigned to α -, β -,
369 and δ - methine protons of chlorophyll a, respectively, as has been already reviewed.⁴²
370 Table S1 in supplementary section explains peridinin peaks assignment in the region of
371 δ_{H} 5.7–7.15 ppm which was only possible due to HSQC experiments and literature data
372 due to the low concentration of this compound. The singlets due to methyl protons of
373 peridinin should be located in the region of δ_{H} 1.0–2.0 ppm but the overlapping found in
374 our spectra with other signals difficulted the assignment of most of them. The presence

375 of other carotenoids could not be established due to their low concentration in the
376 samples.

377 **Metabolic profile of methanolic *A. carterae* biomass extracts.** The overview of
378 compounds of high to mid-range polarity was obtained through extraction with CD₃OD:
379 D₂O KH₂PO₄ buffer (80:20, v/v). The visual inspection of NMR spectra of *A. carterae*
380 biomass extracts from different sets revealed clear differences between them (Figure S3).
381 A tentative identification was made for *A. carterae* methanol:water (80:20 v/v) extracts
382 (Figure 3) and it includes carbohydrates, amino acids, organic acids, polyols, osmolytes,
383 APDs and other related metabolites. Information on proton NMR chemical shifts and
384 coupling constants for the assigned metabolites are described in Table 3. All assignments
385 were also verified with two-dimensional NMR experiments, such as ¹H–¹H TOCSY,
386 ¹H–¹H COSY, ¹H–¹³C HMBC and ¹H–¹³C HSQC, the help of the BBIORFCODE 2
387 database from Bruker, of public NMR databases such as COLMAR,⁴³ and HMDB,⁴⁴ and
388 literature data.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸

389 Figure 3A displays the high field region, from δ_{H} 0.90 to 3.25 ppm, of the ¹H NMR
390 spectrum of the methanol:water (80:20 v/v) extract of *A. carterae* biomass. Sharp
391 resonance signals due to amino acids (valine, isoleucine, leucine, threonine, alanine,
392 proline, methionine, glutamate, glutamine, lysine, aspartate) and organic acids (acetate,
393 lactate and succinate) appear in this region and were assigned in accordance with previous
394 literature and matching chemical shifts retrieved from databases cited previously. Many
395 of these metabolites were also found in the microalgae *Pleurochrysis carterae* (under the
396 same phylum Haptophyta) by Zhou, *et al.*⁴⁹ and in the diatom *Chaetoceros calcitrans* as
397 reported by Azizan, *et al.*⁵⁰. A series of broad peaks also appear in this region and are
398 attributable to the fatty acids, whose assignment was previously discussed in the analysis
399 of chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extracts. 2D NMR experiments helped us in the

400 analysis of more difficult assignments owing to overlapping of other signals, such as the
401 broad signals of fatty acids. For example, the doublets of doublets at δ_{H} 2.66 and 2.86
402 ppm were assigned to aspartate on the basis of the cross-peaks observed in two-
403 dimensional TOCSY spectrum, and thanks to the correlation with the ^{13}C signal located
404 at δ_{C} 35.7 ppm visible in the HSQC spectrum.

405 Figure 3B shows the middle field region of the ^1H NMR spectrum (from δ_{H} 3.25 to
406 5.45 ppm), where the main signals arise from carbohydrates moieties which partially
407 overlap with the amino acids R-CH peaks. Again, the analysis of TOCSY allowed the
408 unequivocal assignment of these compounds. Among carbohydrates, small amounts of
409 glucose and galactose were identified through the doublets at δ_{H} 5.14 (α -configuration)
410 and 4.52 (β -configuration) and at δ_{H} 5.18 (α -configuration) and 4.47 (β -configuration),
411 respectively, and through its correlations by 2D heteronuclear experiments. The signals
412 belonging to glycerol were easily identified by two doublets of doublets at δ_{H} 3.52 and
413 3.60 ppm. Resonances for some others compounds such as the amino acid glycine and its
414 derivatives sarcosine (*N*-methylglycine) and betaine (trimethylglycine) and betaine’s
415 biosynthetic precursor choline were also identified. Betaine is an important osmolyte in
416 maintaining osmotic balance and stabilizing the quaternary structure of complex proteins
417 under abiotic stresses.⁵¹ Betaine and its precursor choline are commonly found in marine
418 particulates containing natural assemblages of marine plankton.⁵² Other osmolytes
419 commonly found in wide range of taxa of microalgae are dimethyl sulfide (DMS) and
420 dimethylsulphoniopropionate (DMSP),⁵³⁻⁵⁴ which participate in several phytoplankton
421 physiological functions. However, neither of these metabolites were found in *A. carterae*
422 biomass. Signals assigned to APDs were also found in this region and their correct
423 assignment is given in the next section.

424 Figure 3C shows the low field region, from δ_{H} 5.40 to 8.80 ppm, of the ^1H NMR
425 spectrum of *A. carterae* methanol:water (80:20 v/v) extract. The signals in this range are
426 the weakest and arise mostly from aromatic groups of amino acids, such as phenylalanine,
427 tryptophan and tyrosine, and from nitrogenous bases, mostly uracil. The two singlets
428 located at δ_{H} 6.65 and 8.42 ppm belong to fumarate and formate, respectively.
429 Characteristic ^1H signals at δ_{H} 7.20 and 8.18 ppm could be ascribed to histidine. Two
430 *trans*-olefinic ($J = 15.9$ Hz) signals at δ_{H} 6.35 (δ_{C} 121.5 Hz) and 7.43 ppm (δ_{C} 137.4 ppm)
431 probably belong to a phenylpropanoid compound (e.g. caffeic, ferulic or coumaric acid),
432 which have a great commercial value in pharmacological and other industrial fields.
433 Unfortunately, its unequivocal identification was not possible due to its low
434 concentration.

435 Interestingly, broad peaks at δ_{H} 6.51, 5.99, 5.67 and 5.38 ppm were observed in the
436 spectrum and were tentatively ascribed to an oxylipin-type compound. Oxylipins are a
437 large and structurally diverse family of lipid metabolites generated by oxidation of
438 PUFAs, mainly EPA and DHA,⁵⁵ and are involved in the regulation of growth
439 developmental processes and in the defense against biotic and abiotic stresses like
440 drought, mechanical wounding, UV-radiation, temperature and pathogens.⁵⁶ Such
441 compounds have a broad range of activities, are anti-inflammatory and vasodilatory.⁵⁷
442 Microalgae can produce a wide range of different biologically active oxylipins.⁵⁷ Table
443 S2 in supplementary section includes δ_{H} and δ_{C} information on the oxylipin structure
444 found in *A. carterae* biomass. Assignments were confirmed by one and two-dimensional
445 TOCSY. Further studies are in progress in our group in order to promote their formation
446 in higher extent and in the optimization of their isolation procedures.

447 **Assignment of APDs class of metabolites.** As stated above, the assignment of APDs
448 metabolites was possible with the help of 2D-NMR experiments, HR-MS and tandem

449 MS. A careful inspection of the two-dimensional ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC spectrum of the extract
450 itself allowed identifying key fragments that are common in most of the amphidinolides
451 already known. Peak assignment of the amphidinol identified on *A. carterae*
452 methanol:water (80:20 v/v) extracts is given in Table S3. Interestingly, HMBC
453 correlations of signals at δ 4.09/211.5 (H11/C13) and 4.04/211.5 (H15/C13) permitted to
454 unravel the β,β' -dihydroketone functionality, cross peaks at δ 5.07/149.5 (H69/C42),
455 5.07/26.1 (H69/C41) and 4.99/75.2 (H69/C43) identified the exomethylene moiety, and
456 at δ 4.92/33.4 (H65/C63) and 2.00/28.7 (H63/C61) the terminal olefin (Figure 4).

457 In addition, the amphidinol present in the extract did not contain the conjugated triene
458 moiety present in amphidinols such as linshuiol,¹⁵ or amphidinol 3,⁵ what points to
459 amphidinol A or karatungiol A,⁵⁸ as the polyketide found in our extract. The study of the
460 high resolution MS data from the $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (80:20, v/v) extracts led to observe the
461 detection of the main m/z signals of 1361.8571 in positive polarity and 1417.8135 in
462 negative polarity (after logically subtracting the background signals), respectively. The
463 first one corresponded to a predicted molecular formula of $\text{C}_{69}\text{H}_{126}\text{O}_{24}\text{Na}$ (with 2.5 ppm
464 of accuracy error and a very satisfactory isotopic pattern prediction (i-FIT)). This finding
465 demonstrates that the substance under study was $\text{C}_{69}\text{H}_{126}\text{O}_{24}$ (exhibiting a signal
466 corresponding to $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$), accounting for 7 formal unsaturations, what definitively
467 confirms the lack of the triene subunit, and more importantly, focus the structure on
468 amphidinol A instead of karatungiol A. The TOF MS negative mode spectrum provided
469 a prevalent m/z signal of 1417.8135, which corresponds to $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$ of amphidinol B
470 ($\text{C}_{69}\text{H}_{125}\text{O}_{27}\text{S}^-$ (prediction error = 0.4 ppm and excellent i-FIT)) and provides the
471 diagnostic M+2 isotopic cluster of sulfur-containing entities. Thus, the coexistence of
472 amphidinol B together with amphidinol A was proved. Our results are therefore in

473 agreement with those found by Cutignano, *et al.*⁶, who were able to isolate amphidinols
474 A and B (the 7-sulfate derivative) from strains of *A. carterae*.

475 The presence of amphidinol B in our extracts was further confirmed, after assigning to
476 it the *m/z* signal of 1463.7921 (detected in positive polarity), which perfectly matched
477 with the ion [M-H+2Na]⁺ (C₆₉H₁₂₅O₂₇Na₂S⁺) and had been previously observed by
478 the just cited research team.

479 The most prevalent fragmentation signals achieved by ESI-IT MS for amphidinol A
480 (*m/z* 1361.8 as precursor ion) were the following ones (relative intensity (%) among
481 brackets): 1085.6 (100), 687.4 (56.7), 1143.5 (27.1), 963.6 (12.1) and 745.4 (11.1) (Figure
482 S4). When amphidinol B (*m/z* 1417.8 considered as precursor ion) was fragmented, the
483 *m/z* signals (and their relative intensities) of 1019.5 (100), 785 (10), 296.9 (10) and 355.1
484 (10) were registered within the MS/MS spectrum (Figure S4). The described
485 fragmentations patterns are quite similar to those obtained by Cutignano, *et al.*⁶, in
486 particular regarding the *m/z* signals detected in the MS/MS spectra (the relative intensity
487 of the fragments differed, but that has obviously to do with the cut off energy and
488 amplitude applied).

489 **PCA of spectroscopic profiles of *A. carterae*.** The untargeted metabolite profile for
490 the microalgal species *A. carterae* was generated using NMR spectroscopy and was
491 investigated through multivariate analysis performed over ¹H NMR data, first using
492 principal component analysis (PCA). The PCA scores and loadings plots are represented
493 in Figure 5. The PCA scores analysis (Figure 5A) showed clear discrimination between
494 *A. carterae* biomass cultures collected from the 5 different experimental sets, assuring a
495 differential metabolic profiling between them. The PCA loadings plot of Figure 5B
496 reveals the metabolites responsible for the discrimination pattern for each culture set. The
497 position of each group in a given direction in the scores plot is influenced by the

498 metabolites (loadings) that are in the same direction in the loadings graph. Thus, the
499 loadings farthest from the center of the graph represent the spectral areas (containing
500 specific metabolite signals) that have a greater influence on the discrimination observed.

501 To obtain an overall picture of the metabolic variations during each cultivation period,
502 a hierarchically clustered heatmap (Figure 6) was obtained from a total of 50
503 discriminating buckets containing significantly altered microalgal metabolites. The
504 heatmap provides an intuitive visualization of the data matrices and useful insights about
505 dysregulated metabolite features and sample grouping. Thus, it is possible to visualize
506 which metabolites increase or decrease in a particular sample group. The results clearly
507 established that the samples collected at different sets were remarkably different in terms
508 of the expression levels of metabolites. Briefly, biomass samples collected in sets 4 and
509 5 show a general increase in the levels of free amino acids (e.g. alanine, threonine, valine,
510 isoleucine, leucine, lysine, glycine, proline, asparagine, tyrosine, phenylalanine,
511 tryptophan), mostly for set 4. Analogous to the results of the amino acids, the levels of
512 carbohydrates (glucose, galactose) were also higher at sets 4 and 5. Set 4 showed a
513 maximum content on chlorophyll a and peridinin. Oxylipin compound (from PUFA
514 oxidation) and glycerol increased for set 1, while set 2 showed a maximum content of
515 SFAs and MUFAs. DHA and EPA showed a peak of production on sets 3 and 5,
516 respectively. This profile exhibited by *A. carterae* is in line with others reported
517 previously for the same species photoautotrophically grown. APDs are also clearly more
518 concentrated at set 5, being in accordance with our previous results on hemolytic activity
519 (Figure 1).

520 A heatmap of correlations was also performed (Figure 7), where metabolite-metabolite
521 correlation analysis was conducted by Spearman rank correlation coefficient analysis.
522 The heatmap revealed several “hot spots” of highly correlated buckets, which may contain

523 peaks coming from the same metabolite or metabolites that belong to the same class (e.g.,
524 amino acids), or more importantly, that share the same physiological functions in the cell
525 and/or intermediate the same biochemical pathways.

526 **Metabolic variations due to increased daily irradiance.** In illuminated microalgae
527 cultures, inorganic carbon is fixed into storage carbon compounds during the light period,
528 such as carbohydrates and lipids, which are consumed in the dark period to accommodate
529 vital cell functions.⁵⁹ As a result, for the choice of the illumination regime in industrial
530 microalgal cultivations, such as continuous light or a light dark cycle, the length of the
531 photoperiod and the light intensity could markedly affect both the growth and the biomass
532 composition of microalgae. Herein, the cellular content of biomass metabolites
533 (especially the photosynthesis-related ones) in relation to light conditions was monitored.
534 PLS-DA models were generated with NMR data from *A. carterae* biomass harvested in
535 the transitions characterized by an increase in the daily mean irradiance received by the
536 culture (Y_o) according to Table 1: (i) from sets 1 and 2 (Figure 8A) and (ii) from sets 4
537 and 5 (Figure 8B), henceforth referred to as T1-2 and T4-5 respectively. A PLS model
538 allows to relate two data matrices (X and Y) to each other by a linear multivariate model
539 and it is useful to understand how the X variables are influenced by a Y variable, in this
540 study, the Y_o . The models were interpreted as good models by means of R² and Q²
541 cumulative value with scores of 0.976 and 0.999 and of 0.918 and 0.999 for models of
542 Figure 8A and 8B, respectively. The R² value gives overview of the fitness of the model
543 and Q² value describes the prediction quality of the model. Both values are close to 1 and
544 represent a good performance model.²⁷

545 *Amino acids.* In the T1-2 from 286 to 430 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, the metabolism of amino acids
546 was affected differently compared to the above-described changes between the sets
547 gathered in two groups, that is, from sets 1-2 to sets 4-5. Hence, four amino acids (valine,

548 isoleucine, proline, tyrosine and histidine) were not up-regulated in response to a higher
549 Y_o in set 2 relative to set 1 (see contributions plot at Fig. 8C). The transition T4-5 (Y_o from
550 430 to 573 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) accentuated that trend inducing down-regulation of the most of
551 amino acids, while their levels remained still clearly above those measured in the sets 1,
552 2 and 3, as it is shown in Figure 8D. This progression may be partially associated with an
553 excess of illumination in set 5 compared to set 4. Excess light energy that cannot be
554 converted into chemical energy is dissipated by means of protective light-regulating, non-
555 photochemical quenching (NPQ) mechanisms. Photoinhibition really is the net result of
556 light-induced damage to PSII, counteracted by the cellular repair mechanisms and by
557 photoprotective processes (i.e. NPQ). Thus, photodamage does not suddenly begin at a
558 given irradiance but occurs whenever cells are illuminated. Light stress becomes
559 metabolically evident if the rate of photoinhibition is the same order (light saturation) or
560 exceeds (photodamage) the rates of NPQ and PSII repair.⁶⁰ The damage of PSII consists
561 of initial oxidation events of the D1 and D2 proteins by both $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ and $\text{HO}\cdot$ involved in
562 the photoinhibitory process. Specific amino acid residues of the D1 and D2 proteins that
563 are oxidized by $\text{HO}\cdot$, and, possibly $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ have been recently identified during
564 illumination.⁶¹ These observations allow conjuring a negative impact on the synthesis of
565 amino acids in microalga under light stress. In this sense, the sets 4 and 5 may have been
566 dominated by a light-saturated growth.

567 In keeping with an earlier study with *Scenedesmus obliquus*,⁶² the effects of irradiance
568 level (Y_o) and photoperiod length may be overlapped. Table 1 shows that Y_o in sets 1 to 4
569 was provided including a darkness period, while Y_o in set 5 was provided continuously in
570 a 24 h light cycle. Amino acid contents in *S. obliquus* were higher in all growth phases
571 for cultures with photoperiod in the illumination cycle compared to cultures illuminated
572 continuously.⁶² Therefore, irradiance level and existence of a darkness period in the

573 illumination cycle are two factor that trigger synthesis of amino acids by different routes.
574 Increased irradiance would favor the cell growth and protein production, while light/dark
575 cycles would stimulate the accumulation of free amino acids in the intracellular
576 environment during the darkness period, but at lower average growth rates.⁶² Thus, the
577 data in Figures of the transition T4-5 do not permit a definite conclusion to be drawn
578 about amino acid metabolism of *A. carterae*. There is, therefore, the possibility that the
579 down-regulation of the most amino acids in T4-5 is the net result of the effect of light
580 excess, darkness absence and increased *Yo*.

581 On the other hand, it is hard to establish meticulous comparison with data reported in
582 the literature for other microalgae because of the complexity of amino acids synthesis
583 pathways depends on the species. To further support this point, a few examples are
584 highlighted below. Glutamate and glutamine are a critical nitrogen entry point because
585 many other amino acids and cofactors are produced from them, as reported for non-
586 dinoflagellate microalgae.⁶³ Results presented herein showed the glutamate content in *A.*
587 *carterae* did not varied, but glutamine content increased in T1-2 and decreased in T4-5.
588 Interestingly, set 1-4 had a darkness period in the light regimes fixed, while set 5 is not.
589 Algae such as *Dunaliella* accumulated glutamine under continuous light compared to L/D
590 cycle.⁶⁴ In contrast, glutamine was not detected in *Scenedesmus obliquus* cultures, but
591 glutamate concentration was higher with L/D cycle at all growth phases than with
592 continuous light.⁶² Differently, the relative abundances of glutamate and glutamine in
593 *Clamydomonas renhardtii* did not change during photocclimation to high irradiance
594 under constant L/D cycle; although plausible explanations were given, they were also
595 inconclusive.⁶⁵ Surprising results were also reported for the haptophyte *Isochrysis* sp.,
596 because its amino acids content and profile were found to change little with the irradiance
597 varied from 50 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ to 1000 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.⁶⁶

598 *Fatty acids and pigments.* Changes on *A. carterae* lipidic and pigment profiles along
599 with the increased irradiance followed patterns that were reported and discussed by
600 Molina-Miras, *et al.*¹⁷. In the T1-2 the content on SFAs and MUFAs increased, while the
601 general amounts of PUFAs decreased except for DHA whose content slightly increased
602 (see Figure 8C). Oxylipin compound from PUFA peroxidation also decreased along with
603 glycerol.

604 The transition T4-5 promoted less evident changes on the fatty acid profile compared
605 to the transition T1-2, as also evidenced by the heatmap of Figure 5. Still, it was noticeable
606 a slight increase on ω -3 fatty acids (DHA and EPA). This pattern seems to confirm light-
607 saturated growth in sets 4 and 5. The content on the pigments chlorophyll a and peridinin
608 decreased systematically with the increased irradiance on both transitions T1-2 and T4-5
609 (Figure S5). This is due to a photoacclimation regulating the size of the light harvesting
610 antennae based on the irradiance level received by the cells.¹⁷ The highest concentration
611 for both compounds was observed at set 4, with a 18/6 light/dark illumination regime and
612 using a $f/2 \times 3$ (N:P=5) as culture medium.

613 *APDs.* The transition T4-5 characterized by a 24 h light cycle in set 5, also induced
614 down-regulation of the most of primary sugars as observed for amino acids (Figure 8D),
615 while their levels remained still clearly above those measured in the rest of sets, as it is
616 shown in Figure 6. This reflects the light-stress regulation mainly through increased
617 carbohydrate metabolism which might divert from amino acids and proteins synthesis to
618 support the biosynthesis of defensive compounds.⁶⁷ This is may be the case of APDs.
619 These polyketides have the glycolate as the starter unit of polyketide synthases assembly
620 leading to this class of metabolites.⁵ Glycolate is oxidized to glyoxylate, and this is
621 metabolized to glycine.⁵ As synthesis and metabolism of glycolate is boosted in algae as
622 a mechanism to protect cells against light-stress,⁶⁵ it would be feasible to expect an

623 increase of APDs in biomass produced in the set 5 (see Figure 1). Indeed, the glycine
624 content in the biomass from set 4 and 5 was significantly higher than in the rest of sets.

625 **Metabolic variations due to increased nutrient availability.** C and N allocation due
626 to increased nutrient availability was investigated in this section. Figure 9 shows a PLS-
627 DA model created with NMR data from *A. carterae* biomass from sets 2-4, that evaluates
628 the effect on the increased concentration levels of the f/2 medium nutrients (f/2 × 1-3). In
629 the transition from set 2 to set 4, general content on SFAs and MUFAs decreased while
630 PUFAs ω-3 increased (but mostly from set 2 to 3). The content on free amino acids and
631 sugars on set 4 was the highest. Due to the increase on nutrient availability, the assimilated
632 N was re-distributed via the glutamate–glutamine pathway and the corresponding
633 transaminase pathways and stored as amino acids and intermediate molecules, including
634 proline, alanine, arginine, and succinate, via the GABA pathway and the TCA cycle. In
635 C flow pathways, the new assimilated C is re-distributed into storage sugar molecules and
636 C-containing compounds, such as glucose 6-phosphate (G6P), fructose 6-phosphate
637 (F6P), phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP), lactate and leucine, via the GABA pathway and the
638 TCA cycle, or can be diverted into storage lipid biosynthesis.⁶⁷ Nutrient availability also
639 influenced pigment synthesis, causing a general increase on chlorophyll a and peridinin
640 until they reached their maximum at set 4 (also evidenced on Figure S5).

641 **Correlation between hemolytic activity and NMR data.** The fast monitoring of
642 bioactive compounds is important to quickly understand if the applied culture conditions
643 are favoring their production. We aim to develop a simple and direct quantification
644 method of such molecules by NMR. To do so, the absolute integral of the peak at δ_{H} 5.07
645 ppm along the different ¹H NMR spectra of methanol:water (80:20 v/v) extracts of *A.*
646 *carterae* was calculated and correlated with hemolytic activity by a univariate simple
647 linear regression (Figure 10A). Despite this high correlation obtained ($R^2 = 0.97$), other

648 compounds may also contribute to the hemolytic activity. To confirm the lack of this
649 interference from other compounds, supervised multivariate data analysis techniques
650 were applied to find a correlation between NMR data and hemolytic data of *A. carterae*
651 biomass. Figure 10B and 11C represent a PLS scores and loadings plots, respectively,
652 from ¹H NMR and hemolytic activity data. The loadings plot of Figure 10C allows to
653 visualize all the buckets from methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and chloroform:methanol
654 (80:20 v/v) extracts that are more correlated to the hemolytic activity, which are the
655 closest to the blue point representing the hemolytic activity. Finally, the contribution plot
656 of Figure 10D allows us to confirm that from all the discriminating metabolites, APDs
657 (contribution bar in red) have the highest correlation with hemolytic activity. The other
658 metabolites having high correlation factors with hemolytic activity do not necessarily
659 contribute directly to this activity but may be present in higher quantities on samples from
660 set 5 due to a deviation of metabolic pathways in order to produce APDs compounds or
661 for other undetermined reasons.

662 In conclusion, this study allowed to apply a metabolomics approach using NMR
663 spectroscopy and multivariate data analysis to investigate metabolic changes on a long-
664 term (>170 days) culture of the dinoflagellate microalga *A. carterae* in a raceway
665 photobioreactor operating in semicontinuous mode and by altering concentration levels
666 of the f/2 medium nutrients and daily mean irradiance. Increased daily irradiance
667 contributed for the decrease of the major pigments (chlorophyll a and peridinin), and for
668 a general increase of SFAs, MUFAs and also of DHA (while for other PUFAs it was the
669 opposite). Increased nutrient availability lead to an increase of sugars, amino acids, PUFA
670 ω-3 contents and of pigments chlorophyll a and peridinin, accompanied by a decrease on
671 SFAs and MUFAs. The last set operating with 24 h light cycle showed a 3-fold increase
672 on APDs, maybe due to a stress-mediated response caused by photoacclimation. As

673 expected, the spectral buckets containing APDs peaks showed to be those more correlated
674 with hemolytic activity. The use of NMR and metabolomics techniques have confirmed
675 for the first time to be a suitable method to accompany the production of APDs class of
676 compounds without the need of tedious isolation methods.

677

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. Average equivalent saponin potency (ESP) of *A. carterae* culture from the different experimental sets (described in Table 1).

Figure 2. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of the chloroform-methanol extract of *A. carterae* biomass from set 5 (see Table 1). Fatty acids assignments are given in Table 3. Abbreviations: DG – diacylglycerols, DHA – docosahexaenoic acid, EPA – eicosapentaenoic acid, FA – fatty acids, PUFA – polyunsaturated fatty acids, TAG – triacylglycerols, UFA – unsaturated fatty acids, ω -3 – omega 3 FA.

Figure 3. Expansions A, B and C of a characteristic ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of the $\text{CD}_3\text{OD}:\text{D}_2\text{O}:\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4$ buffer (80:20, v/v) extract of *A. carterae* biomass from set 5 (see Table 1). Metabolite assignments are given in Table 2. Abbreviations: ala – alanine, APDs – amphidinolides and amphidinolds class, asp – aspartate, DG – diacylglycerols, FA – fatty acids, gal – galactose, glc – glucose, gln – glutamine, glu – glutamate, gly – glycine, his – histidine, ile – isoleucine, leu – leucine, lys – lysine, met – methionine, phe – phenylalanine, pro – proline, PUFA – polyunsaturated fatty acids, TAG – triacylglycerols, thr – threonine, trp – tryptophan, tyr – tyrosine, UFA – unsaturated fatty acids, val – valine, ω -3 – omega 3 FA.

Figure 4. Structure of amphidinol A (R = H) and amphidinol B (R=SO₃H) showing with arrows the diagnostic HMBC cross peaks.

<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b02821> analysis (PCA) scores (A) and loadings (B) plots resulted

from the analysis of ^1H NMR spectra of both methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extracts of *A. carterae* biomass for the five experimental sets corresponding to semi-continuous cultures (described in Table 1). PCA loading plot reveals the spectral regions (buckets) from methanol:water (80:20 v/v, circles) and chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v, triangles) *A. carterae* extracts, which are located according to the discrimination pattern of the scores plot.

Figure 6. Heatmap showing z-scores of 50 discriminatory buckets from methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v, signaled with ‘) extracts of *A. carterae* biomass and their assigned metabolites for the 5 different experimental sets. The heatmap construction was based on Euclidean distances and Ward clustering. X axis represents the average of eight biological replicates for each culture set (from 1 to 5). The color scheme represents the variation on metabolic content among the 5 groups in a scale from dark blue (lowest content) to dark red (highest content). The center for each bucket (ppm) of 0.04 ppm widths is represented. Abbreviations: ala – alanine, APDs – amphidinolides and amphidinols class, asp – aspartate, bet – betaine, chl a – chlorophyll a, DG – diacylglycerols, DHA - docosahexaenoic acid, EPA – eicosapentaenoic acid, FA – fatty acids, gal – galactose, glc – glucose, gln – glutamine, glu – glutamate, gly – glycine, his – histidine, ile – isoleucine, leu – leucine, lys – lysine, met – methionine, MUFA – monounsaturated fatty acids, phe – phenylalanine, pro – proline, phenylprop. – phenylpropanoid, PUFA – polyunsaturated fatty acids, putr – putrescine, SFA – saturated fatty acids, TAG – triacylglycerols, thr – threonine, trp – tryptophan, tyr – tyrosine, UFA – unsaturated fatty acids, val – valine, n-3 – omega 3 FA.

Figure 7. Heatmap of correlations between 50 selected buckets and their assigned metabolites from *A. carterae* biomass methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and

chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v), signaled with ‘) extracts. Each square represents the Spearman’s correlation coefficient between the metabolite of the column with that of the row in a color scheme ranging from dark blue (lowest correlation) to dark red (highest correlation). The center for each bucket (ppm) of 0.04 ppm widths is represented. Abbreviations: ala – alanine, APDs – amphidinolides and amphidinolds class, asp – aspartate, bet – betaine, chl a – chlorophyll a, DG – diacylglycerols, DHA - docosahexaenoic acid, EPA- eicosapentaenoic acid, FA – fatty acids, gal – galactose, glc – glucose, gln – glutamine, glu – glutamate, gly – glycine, his – histidine, ile – isoleucine, leu – leucine, lys – lysine, met – methionine, MUFA – monounsaturated fatty acids, phe – phenylalanine, pro – proline, phenylprop. – phenylpropanoid, PUFA – polyunsaturated fatty acids, putr – putrescine, SFA – saturated fatty acids, TAG – triacylglycerols, thr – threonine, trp – tryptophan, tyr – tyrosine, UFA – unsaturated fatty acids, val – valine, n-3 – omega 3 FA.

Figure 8. PLS-DA scores and contribution plots obtained from ¹H NMR data of both methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extracts of *A. carterae* biomass from sets 1-2 (A and C, respectively), and from sets 4-5 (B and D, respectively). Daily irradiance was represented with 1: 286, 2: 430 and 3: 573 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Scaling was done to Unit Variance. An increase in the daily mean irradiance was observed in the transition from 1 to 2 and from 4 to 5 according to Table 1. The contribution plots include list of the metabolites that most increase (upper bars) or decrease (down bars) with increased irradiance through the analysis of their VIP "variable importance in projection" values (VIP>1.0). Abbreviations: ala – alanine, APDs – amphidinolides and amphidinolds class, asp – aspartate, bet – betaine, chl a – chlorophyll a, DG – diacylglycerols, DHA - docosahexaenoic acid, EPA- eicosapentaenoic acid, FA – fatty acids, gal – galactose, glc – glucose, gln – glutamine, glu – glutamate, gly – glycine, his – histidine, ile – isoleucine, leu – leucine, lys – lysine, met – methionine, MUFA –

<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b02821>, phe – phenylalanine, pro – proline, phenylprop. –

phenylpropanoid, PUFA – polyunsaturated fatty acids, putr – putrescine, SFA – saturated fatty acids, TAG – triacylglycerols, thr – threonine, trp – tryptophan, tyr – tyrosine, UFA – unsaturated fatty acids, val – valine, n-3 – omega 3 FA.

Figure 9. PLS-DA scores (A) and contribution (B) plots obtained from ¹H NMR data of both methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extracts of *A. carterae* biomass from sets 2 – 4, along with an increase on concentration levels of the f/2 medium nutrients (f/2 × 1-3) according to Table 1. The contribution plots include list of the metabolites that most increase (upper bars) or decrease (down bars) with increased nutrient availability through the analysis of their VIP "variable importance in projection" values (VIP>1.0). Abbreviations: ala – alanine, asp – aspartate, bet- betaine, chl a – chlorophyll a, EPA- eicosapentaenoic acid, FA – fatty acids, gal – galactose, glc – glucose, gln – glutamine, gly – glycine, ile – isoleucine, leu – leucine, lys – lysine, met – methionine, MUFA – monounsaturated fatty acids, phe – phenylalanine, pro – proline, Putr – putrescine, SFA – saturated fatty acids, thr – threonine, trp – tryptophan, tyr – tyrosine, val – valine.

Figure 10. (A) Univariate simple linear regression between hemolytic activity and the absolute integrals of the peak at δ_{H} 5.07 ppm assigned to APDs; PLS scores contributions (B) and loadings (C) plots obtained from ¹H NMR data of both methanol:water (80:20 v/v) and chloroform:methanol (80:20 v/v) extracts of *A. carterae* biomass for all the sets (X-data) and from hemolytic activity (Y-data). (D) List of the metabolites that contribute most to the discrimination of the PLS model through the analysis of their VIP "variable importance in projection" values (VIP>1.0). Abbreviations: ala – alanine, APDs – amphidinolides and amphidinolds class, DHA - docosahexaenoic acid, EPA- eicosapentaenoic acid, FA – fatty acids, leu – leucine, lys – lysine, MUFA –

– unsaturated fatty acids.

<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b02821> Table 1. Description of five semicontinuous culture experiments from which harvested

biomass was used. Five experimental sets were defined in terms of the daily mean irradiance Y_o received by the culture at different light/dark illumination regimes and initial concentration of nutrients in the culture medium based on the f/2 composition (nitrogen to phosphorous molar ratio in the culture medium was fixed to 5).

Set	Day of culture	Light/Dark cycle, hours	Y_o, $\mu\text{Em}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2}$	Nutrients
1	36	12/12	286	f/2 × 1
2	64	18/6	430	f/2 × 1
3	99	18/6	430	f/2 × 2
4	122	18/6	430	f/2 × 3
5	161	24/0	573	f/2 × 3

Table 1. Peak assignments of the fatty acids identified on *A. carterae* chloroform:methanol

(80:20 v/v) extracts

Metabolite	Chemical assignment	δ_{H} (ppm)	δ_{C} (ppm)
Sterols			
Sterol (cholesterol)	–CH ₃	0.73	13.6
Lipids: glycerides			
Triacylglycerols	OCH (<i>sn</i> -2) glycerol	5.26	69.6
	OCH ₂ (<i>sn</i> -1,3) glycerol	4.30, 4.16	62.0
1,2-Diacylglycerols	OCH (<i>sn</i> -2) glycerol	5.08	72.0
	OCH (<i>sn</i> -1) glycerol	4.31, 4.21	62.4
	HO–CH ₂ (<i>sn</i> -3) glycerol	3.71	62.8
Lipids: glycerophospholipids			
Phospholipids (PL) + Glycolipids (GL)	OCH ₂ glycerol	4.45-4.54	~61
Lipids: Fatty acid chains			
Saturated fatty chains	–CH ₃	0.87 (t)	13.7
	–(CH ₂) _n –	1.23–1.34	23.0–32.0
	–CH ₂ –CH ₂ –COOR	1.60	24.7
	–CH ₂ –COOR	2.28	34.2
Monounsaturated fatty acid chain (MUFA)	–CH ₃	0.87 (t)	13.7
	–(CH ₂) _n –	1.23–1.34	23.0–32.0
	–CH ₂ –CH ₂ –COOR	1.60	24.7
	–CH ₂ –CH=CH–	2.01	27.6
	–CH ₂ –COOR	2.28	34.2
	–CH=CH–	5.40–5.32	128.2
Docosahexaenoic fatty acid chain C22:6 (DHA)	–CH ₃	0.96 (t)	14.1
	–CH ₂ –CH=CH–	2.07	20.8
	–CH ₂ –CH ₂ –COOR	2.36	33.8
	=CH–CH ₂ –CH=	2.86–2.76	25.5
	–CH=CH–	5.40–5.28	127.8–131.7
Eicosapentaenoic fatty acid chain C20:5 (EPA)	–CH ₃	0.96 (t)	14.1
	–CH ₂ –CH ₂ –COOR	1.68	24.6
	–CH ₂ –CH=CH–	2.07	20.8

$-\text{CH}_2-\text{COOR}$	2.28	34.2
$=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$	2.86–2.76	25.5
$-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$	5.40–5.28	127.8–131.7

Table 3. Identifications and their signature peak (ppm) values from ¹H NMR

spectroscopy from *A. carterae* methanol:water (80:20 v/v) extracts

Metabolite	δ_H (ppm), J (Hz)
<i>Amino acids</i>	
Valine (Val)	1.01 (d, <i>J</i> = 7.0 Hz), 1.06 (d, <i>J</i> = 7.0 Hz)
Isoleucine (Ile)	0.95 (t, <i>J</i> = 7.2 Hz), 1.02 (d, <i>J</i> = 7.0 Hz)
Leucine (Leu)	0.98 (m)
Threonine (Thr)	1.33 (d, <i>J</i> = 6.5 Hz), 4.18 (m)
Alanine (Ala)	1.47 (d, <i>J</i> = 7.2 Hz)
Proline (Pro)	1.99 (m), 3.29 (m), 3.40 (m), 4.02 (m)
Methionine (Met)	2.12 (s), 2.63 (t, <i>J</i> = 7.5 Hz)
Glutamate (Glu)	2.07 (m), 2.10 (m), 2.35 (m)
Glutamine (Gln)	2.11 (m), 2.46 (m)
Glycine (Gly)	3.44 (s)
Aspartate (Asp)	2.66 (dd, <i>J</i> = 17.5; 9.3 Hz), 2.86 (dd, <i>J</i> = 17.5; 3.6 Hz)
Lysine (Lys)	1.49 (m), 1.72 (m), 1.88 (m), 2.97 (t, <i>J</i> = 7.9 Hz)
Tryptophan (Trp)	7.07 (td, <i>J</i> = 7.7; 0.9 Hz), 7.14 (m), 7.24 (s), 7.40 (dt, <i>J</i> = 8.1; 0.9 Hz), 7.70 (dt, <i>J</i> = 7.7; 0.9 Hz)
Tyrosine (Tyr)	3.05 (dd, <i>J</i> = 8.7; 14.8 Hz), 3.21 (dd, <i>J</i> = 4.7; 14.8 Hz), 6.80 (d, <i>J</i> = 8.5 Hz), 7.15 (d, <i>J</i> = 8.5 Hz)
Phenylalanine (Phe)	7.29 (m), 7.32 (m), 7.36 (m)
Histidine (His)	7.20 (s), 8.18 (s)
<i>Organic acids</i>	
Lactate	1.34 (d, <i>J</i> = 6.9 Hz), 4.10 (q, <i>J</i> = 6.9 Hz)
Acetate	1.90 (s)
Succinate	2.40 (s)
Fumarate	6.65 (s)
Formate	8.42 (s)
<i>Sugars</i>	
β-galactose (β-gal)	4.47 (d, <i>J</i> = 7.8 Hz)
β-glucose (β-glc)	4.52 (d, <i>J</i> = 7.9 Hz)
α-glucose (α-glc)	5.14 (d, <i>J</i> = 3.7 Hz)
α-galactose (α-gal)	5.18 (d, <i>J</i> = 3.6 Hz)

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Choline	3.23 (s)
Betaine (trimethylglycine)	3.27 (s)

Organosulfur compounds

Sarcosine (methylglycine)	2.71 (s)
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Polyhydric alcohols

Glycerol	3.52 (dd, $J = 11.6; 6.3$ Hz) 3.60 (dd, $J = 11.6; 4.5$ Hz), 3.68 (m)
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Nitrogenous bases

Uracil	5.68 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz), 7.46 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz)
Cytosine	5.91 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 7.47 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz)

Others

Putrescine	1.76 (m), 3.00 (m)
APDs*	4.92 and 4.97 (=CH ₂), 4.99 and 5.07 (=CH ₂), 5.58, 5.79, 5.81
Oxylipin-derivative*	6.51 (m), 5.99 (m)
Phenylpropanoid	6.36 (d, $J = 15.6$ Hz), 7.09, 7.28, 7.39
Cofactors (e.g. ATP, NADPH, etc.)	8.09 (s), 7.93 (s), 8.16 (s), 7.88 (s)

Unkown

Unknown_1	2.55 (s)
Unknown_2	2.92 (d)
Unknown_3 (Pyridine derivative)	8.58, 8.50, 7.82

* Table S2 and S3 show ¹H and ¹³C NMR assignments made for both APDs and oxylipin derivatives.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10